

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14210673

Organizational Politics And Employee Turnover Intention In Nigeria: A Case Study Of Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina State

Ruqaiyat Mohammed Sada¹ & Saad Abdulmumin Kofarbai²

¹Social Studies Department.

Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma, Katsina State, Nigeria

Email address: rooqysa@gmail.com/08066420778

²General Studies Education.

Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsinma, Katsina State, Nigeria

Email address: abdulsaad271@gmail.com/08060729340.

ABSTRACT

This work examines the relationship between organizational politics in relation to employee turnover intention in federal university Dutsinma. A correlational survey research design was employed, in which five leaker scale questioner was applied as an instrument of data collection. A sampled sized population of both academic and nonacademic staff of the university was extracted using crachcie and Morgan table. The validated questionnaire retrieved were analyzed using linear regression and coefficient statics with the aid of the statistical package for social sciences. The result of the survey demonstrated a significant positive relationship between organizational politics in relation to employee turnover intention in Federal University Dutsinma Katsina. The survey recommended that, organizational politics must be dealt with, by creating proper checking administrative mechanisms, and decisively punishing the players of this dirty politics.

Keywords. Organizational Politics, Employee turnover intention, Federal University Dutsinma.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational politics is deliberate pursuance of self interest in an organization, even when those interests goes contrary to the organizational goals. This type of self-desired politics is more harmful and dangerous than open politics (Andrew&katchma2009)

Organizations are made up of different people from different backgrounds with different behaviors, ideologies, characters and believes, and these variations determines how these individuals comprehend issues in organizations.

Organizational politics is the rigorous pursuit of self-ambitions in an organization, either or not these self-ambitions are coterminous and contagious to the organizational objectives. Dubrin (2011) looked at organizational politics as an informal way through which organizational heads try to acquire power through merit or fortunes. Some times in an organization, organizational heads plays silent politics to fulfil his personal desires, this type of politics is the most dangerous in any organizational setting, (Ahmad 20014)

While employee turnover intention is the propensity, the intention, the desire to leave. Turnover intention according to Husain (2012) is the prevailing mental and behavior decision between an employee's choice of either stay or to leave'. Pavez (2018) has opined that, "turnover intention is conscious willfulness of seeking fresh job opportunity at other organizations". While liv (2012) has

presented alternative terms for turnover intention, as intent to leave, intention to leave and propensity to leave”. Many researches tried to demonstrate turnover as the desire to or willingness to leave positions within or across an organization.

Statement of Problem

Managers all over the world must deal with organizational politics and tried to bared employee turnover intention, because they are already existing realities that not only affects organizational progress and growth, but negatively affects the smooth running of organizations. The ubiquitous nature of organizational politics requires that it must be understood and tackled by managers. Empirical researches have been conducted on organizational politics in relation to employee turnover intention by Mba and Stella (2022), Ahmad (2018), Ndama (2019), Elkalil (2017), Mensa (2017). These researches demonstrated that organizational politics has been well and alive in the Nigerian state, in organizations and institutions.

Hence this study is going to investigate critically the impact of organizational politics in relation to employee turnover intention in Federal University Dutsinma in Katsina State.

Research Objectives

The research is aimed at investigating the following.

1. The negative impact of organizational politics in Federal University Dutsinma in Katsina State.
2. The negative impacts of organizational politics on the employee turnover intention in Federal University Dutsinma in Katsina State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Politics

Dubrin (2001) looked at organizational politics as an informal way in which the employers tries to attain power through merit or fortune, their struggle are only done for personal benefits and to acquire extra projects”. Some times in an organization, the employee plays the silent politics activities to fulfill his personal desires, these type of activities are most dangerous and harmful then open politics, Andrew and Kacmar (2019), and Dubrin, (2001) argued that “employee who do not involve in organizational politics show their reaction in two forms, the absenteeism and turnover. According to Daft (2019) low autonomy and task contribute to powerlessness in an individual that increased the politics in the organization. Several studies have been conducted to examine the nature of the relationships among people in the organization to better understand factors motivating individuals to behave in certain ways. Research studies have examined the causes of conflict in organizations. Among other reasons, the researcher believes that perceived organizational politics are one of the behaviors that incur conflicts in the workplace.

Perception of Organizational Politics and Turnover Intention; An overview

Organizational politics may be defined as the behavior that is strategically designed to maximize short-term or long-term self-interest (Ferris, Russ, and Fandt, 1989). According to VigodGado and Drizin-Arnit (2006) organizational politics is pivotal in as much as it contributes to the perceptive of the spontaneous procedures of rivalry and collaborations in the organizations, and their brunt on the employees’ performance in the workplace (2006). Othman (2008) indicates the two facets of organizational politics in his paper in the aspect of justice, trust and job ambiguity, specifically, the negative side involves favoritism and illegal attitude while the positive side involves collective responsibility that is crucial for organizations to get through”. Negative organizational politics are deplored because of the predicaments coated with them and the organizational struggles they generate. On the other hand the combination of common objectives and inspiring teamwork births positive outcomes of organizational politics (Gotsi and Kortezi, 2010)

(Kurchncr, Hawkins and Miller) argue that political behavior is positive when it delivers organizations’ aims and objectives, promotes unity, boosts morale and creates an emotionally stable environment in a workplace”. Furthermore, (Gotsis and Korzi 2010) remarked that effective political conduct could be more beneficial to highest organizational fairness. This effective political conduct is examined in the light of the obligation to bear together the antithetical passion of shareholders, banking on the strength to reach equilibrium between the contending impulses and outlooks of organizational associates.

Augmenting this, Butcher and Oaken (2006) argue that, superintendents who are seriously apprehensive of the politics surrounding in their organizations have a higher tendency to indulge such political attitudes, thus, bolstering impartiality. According to Kutcher and Miller (2006), organizational politics is a major management involvement detailing the eventual impact of political demeanor on the environment and adaptability of an organization (2006). Therefore, if political action is recognized as a logical and valuable element in organizations, then political schemes might be seen as a partnership, bond-formulation or direction (Gotsis and Kortezi, 2010).

Empirical Review

Ahmed (2018) studied organizational politics and turnover intention in private colleges of Pakistan. This study tends to find out if there is a relationship between organizational politics and its three antecedents' (favoritism, pay and promotion and scarcity of resources) on employee turnover intention in private colleges. Data was collected from the respondents using the Multan city. A quantitative method was adopted and regression analysis was used in testing the hypotheses formulated. It was found out from the study that once an organization is involve in favoritism, delayed pay and promotion and struggle for scarcity of resources this will adversely affect the rate of employee turnover.

Despite the vastness of this work on organizational politics and employee turnover intention, the critical issue of insecurity and employee turnover intention in tertiary institutions has not been discussed in the work.

Nwizia, Ojiabo and Alagah (2017) investigated if there is a relationship between organizational politics and employee's job satisfaction in health sector of Rivers State. The study utilized cross sectional research design. A sample size of 274 was employed using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. Questionnaire was the primary source of data used in collecting information from the respondents. 274 copies of questionnaire were distributed while 245 copies were returned. Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient statistic with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used in analyzing the data and testing the hypotheses. From the findings, it was discovered that there is a positive relationship between organizational politics and employee's job satisfaction and it was concluded that organizational politics affects employee's job satisfaction in the health sector of Rivers State. The study therefore recommended that, Management in health sector of Rivers State should emphasize and put more effort in focus positive political behavior that will drive workers' satisfaction in their job and management must place a good and suitable pay structure and also include how pay, bonuses and performance will be assessed.

The above research conducted by Nwizia on organizational politics on job satisfaction in the health sector in rivers state has not in any way touch the relationship between organizational politics and employee turnover intention in relation to insecurity in tertiary institutions, which this research is attempting to investigate.

Elkhalil (2017) studied organizational politics and employee behavior by investigating the comparison between the U.S. and Lebanon. The study aimed at viewing how employees react to organizational politics within the different cultures of employees in U.S and Lebanon. Structured Research questions were implemented to determine the cultural values and how each employee responds differently facing organizational politics. A survey-based research design which included 352 participants, 176 from each country under study was adopted. Structured questionnaire was adopted to elicit the vital information needed to conclude the research. Using SPSS version 23 a correlation matrix using SPSS version, T-test, and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. It was found out that Findings indicated that power distance and gender role differentiations within Lebanese employees has resulted in low motivation, high job related stress among U.S employees.

Despite the fact that this research was conducted empirically on organizational politics on employee low motivation in US and Lebanon, the research did not in any way touch the recent menace of organizational politics in relation to insecurity and employee turnover intention in tertiary institutions. Mensa, (2016) investigated the relationship among Perceived Organizational Politics, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior among 2 selected public sector organizations in Accra. Correlation research design was adopted in collecting data from 160 participants from the Ghana Standards Authority. Perceived organizational Politics scale by Kalmar and Carlson (1997),

Organizational Commitment scale by Cook and Wall (1980) and Organizational Citizenship scale by Moorman and Blakely (1995) were the questionnaires used for the study. It was revealed that there is a negative relationship between employee's Perceived Organizational Politics and Organizational Commitment, negative relationship was also found between Perceived Organizational Politics and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors and a positive relationship between Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The study however did not find any relationship between the dimensions of Perceived Organizational Politics and Commitment.

The above research conducted by Menser on organizational politics and citizenship behavior did not in any way focused on the new tragedy of insecurity in relation to turnover intention in tertiary institutions, which this work is preparing to investigate.

Kaya, Aydin and Ayhan (2016) studied how organizational politics held by different members of the organizations and how these affect the how the members of the organization views organizational justice and how it relates to it employee turnover decisions. In the study, a total of 259 surveys were completed and obtained from different public and private sector personnel. Confirmatory factor analysis and correlation and regression analyses was implemented to determine the relationship between the variables used in the study. Its findings were that that organizational politics had a positive effect on perceived organizational justice and intention to leave.

The above research on organizational politic in relation to organizational justice on turnover intention did not touch the gap of insecurity and employee turnover intention which this study is going to investigate.

Adebusuyi, Olasupo, and Idehen (2013) investigated how workers in a Nigerian university view the nature and insight of organizational politics. A total of three hundred and seventy two (academic and non-academic) staff of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife was selected to fill the questionnaire on Perception of Organizational Politics Scale (POPS). The research data were analyzed to show the mutual perceived organizational politics and how the relationships affect these dimensions of perceived organizational politics. From the study, the results showed that there are seven dimensions of perception of organizational politics which were: General Political Behavior (GPB), Go Along to get Ahead (GAA), Pay and Promotion Policies (PPP), General Political Behavior and Go Along to get Ahead (GPB and GAA) General Political Behavior and Pay and Promotion Policies (GPB and PPP) and all three (GPB, GAA and PPP).

Despite the fact that the above research has a relationship with pay and promotion in relation to turnover intention in tertiary institution, still the research did not include insecurity in relation to employee turnover intention which this work is investigating.

Abbas and Awan (2017) investigated the effect of organizational politics on employee performance in the public organizations in Pakistan. A thorough extensive literature review was carried out to show an empirical perception about the proposed relationships. A total of 15 public sector employees in the organizations in Pakistan were selected. The data was statistically analyzed using regression analysis. After the conclusion of the study, the results showed that organizational politics have a positive effect on employee performance. The study therefore recommended that management needs to understand how employees views the perception of organizational and develop suitable tactics that would curtail the perception of organizational politics and enhance employee performance in the organization.

The above investigation on organizational politics' positive effects on employee performance did not in any way touched the relationship of organizational politics in relation to insecurity and employee turnover intention.

Advani and Shaista (2014) examined the causes and identification of employees' politics and its impact on performance of Banking Industry in Pakistan. Language and caste, experience and position, cultural animosity, religious lobbies, gender discrimination and referral employment were the major variables used in the study. Quantitative and survey research was adopted in the study. Descriptive statistics was used in analyzing the data. . Simple random sampling method was used in selecting 160 employees out of target population. From the study, it was found that there should be a Standardize Human Resource Management i.e. the right person should be posted to the job, bracing courses, conducting orientation on emerging banking and problem solving and meetings with employees should be conducted to resolve problems that may ensue between employees and management and there must be transparency and merit system observed in all matters.

The above research was conducted in relation to favoritism and employee turnover intention; the research also did not include the phenomenon of insecurity and employee turnover intention which this work is investigating.

Employee Turnover

No organization or employer can guarantee any of their employees' employment. However, organizations seek to offer reasonable opportunities to employees, to build their capacities and skills in the marketplace. These will sometimes enable them to find another job alternative in more favorable circumstances, or in cases of job loss or job insecurity, as noted by Long (2012). Subsequently, it can be said that employee turnover is a normal phenomenon which might occur either from the request of the employee or the employer, and the following literature explains this point more specifically.

Even though there has been research into the significance of turnover from scholars and researchers who have produced previously related theories and models, there is a need for an extensive analysis of the field. Within the period of time through the last decade, the issue of turnover has witnessed significant theoretical expansion. Staff turnover has been considered a serious problem, and more recently in the field of human resource management. A thorough debate on turnover has been circulating in the arena of research concerning organizations and management in general, and concerning turnover in particular. This can be built upon to address the more specific questions proposed by this present study.

Rahman and Nas (2013) have defined turnover as an employee that permanently leaves the boundary of the organization. Furthermore, this study has found that skill acquisition, career advancement, and recognition of performance stimulate organizational retention and commitment. It is important to note that organizations attempt to employ the right staff, to improve their skills and capacities through training and skills acquisition, and support them in order to positively influence an organization as a whole. According to Suzuki (2007), employee turnover is a ratio of the number of employees that a company must replace in certain periods of time

Urbancov and Linhartov (2011) defined turnover as a type of intercompany mobility in which another organization may benefit from an employee and gain new knowledge. In this regard, it can be considered a transfer of employees from an organization to one of its competitive rivals. The result of the study by Nienaber and Masibigiri (2012) on employee turnover, which was researched extensively in the USA, Australia, and the UK, speaks of employee turnover in terms of voluntary turnover. Voluntary turnover is described as the unplanned loss of employees who leave the company, when employers would prefer to keep them. Moreover, voluntary turnover has two main types: avoidable or unavoidable. The avoidable type is preventable as it is represented by a change in place of employment, or by early retirement. Meanwhile, the unavoidable (unpreventable) type involves factors which cannot be controlled, such as the death of an employee. This research focuses on avoidable voluntary turnover, the factors causing it, and measures adapted to prevent it.

Meanwhile, on the other long, (2006) have argued that turnover measurement is problematic in essence. There is no agreement on what is voluntary turnover, since it depends on the individual responses into the reasons why an employee might leave his or her workplace. Voluntary employee turnover concerns situations where an employee has the physical opportunity to continue working with the same organization at the time of termination. Hence, the employee is not headed for termination. As companies have no intention to terminate staff in these cases, it must be that voluntary employee turnover cases concern other factors, such as non- mandatory retirement, family resettlement, or the possibility to leave for a better job offer.

Employee Turnover Intention

Employee turnover intentions are the thoughts of the employees regarding voluntary leaving the organization (Whitman, 1999). The intention to quit is probably the most important immediate antecedent of turnover decisions. Turnover intention is used instead of actual turnover because in general the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) suggests that behavior is a good predictor of actual behavior. In fact, researchers have found intent to leave or stay as the strongest predictor of actual turnover (Hendrix, Robbins, & Summers, 1999, Lee & Liu, 2007).

Turnover intention according to Husain and Asif (2012) "is the prevailing mental and behavior decision between an employee's choices that are either to stay or withdraw, and are consequently

connected instantly with actual turnover". Pevez, (2018) have opined that turnover intention is the conscious willfulness of seeking fresh job opportunities at other organizations, meanwhile Liv and Onwuegbuzie (2012) have presented alternative terms for turnover, such as intent to leave, intension to leave and propensity to leave, furthermore, many researchers simply define turnover intention as the desire or willingness to leave a position within an organization or across the organization.

Turnover intention reflects workers deliberate and intentional tendency to leave their job and the organization. Moreover Arshadi, Damiri and Maiar (2013) have argued that, turnover intention is the conscious decision to look for other job opportunities in other organizations, and say that this results from various factors, determinants and causes that lead employees to intent to leave. In that study academic member turnover intention referred to the reluctance of academics to stay in their places of work within the academic environment. As well as the determinants that drives them to take that decision.

Thirapatsakun (2014) divided employee turnover intention into three particular cognitive components. They are; thinking to leave the job; the intention to leave the job, and intention to search for another job. Thirapatsakun (2014) also argued that, there is a connection between actual employee turnover, and turnover intention. Thus in the intention to leave create a direct effects on turnover decisions. An employee's decision to leave has several unwanted consequences, both for the organization and for the employee which functions along many dimensions.

Research by Alexandrov, (2007) developed and tested turnover intention models, which address the consequences frontline employees' views regarding management concerns on turnover intention, together with the concepts of employee's job satisfaction and commitment to the organization.

Another reproach conducted by Ekberg (2009) "stipulated that there are particular physical symptoms of high level turnover intention and low rate of actual turnover in many academic environments, which requires an urgent management solution."

Different researches have demonstrated that high rise in employee turnover intentions might have negative outcomes on the profit and benefit of organization if not handled perfectly, John (2000) have argued that over twenty years ago, the direct and indirect cost of a single line employee quitting was too unimaginable because turnover has been many invisible cost and these invisible cost are the outcome of incoming employees coworkers meticulously identified with incoming employees, coworkers formerly identified with the leaving employees and post being filled while vacant". All these affect negatively the yielding profit of an organization.

Kamal, (2002) and Catharine (2002) further argued that "turnover comprises other costs; such as loss of productivity, loss of talent, loss of sales and management's time, this plainly displays that turnover influences the yielding gain of an organization and if not handled with an iron fist, it will have negative impacts on the profit".

Johnson (2000) has argued that "Educating and employing a replacement particularly academics costs roughly 50 percent of the worker's yearly salary, but the cost do not cease there each time an employee exists an organization, we assume that yielding gain drops in relation to the learning curve involved in understanding the job and the organization". Meaghan (2002) opined that "the failure of thoughtful capital sums to this cost, since not only do organizations lose the human capital and rational capital of the departing employee, but also competitors are probably benefiting these assets".

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This aspect of research is concerned with the method and procedure in carrying out this study. Hence, this research is going to be conducted using quantitative method, where five liker scale questionnaire is going to be applied to the sampled size of the population, the data collected is going to be analyzed using linear regression statistics with the aid of statistical package for social science.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1 How likely organizational politics affects employee turnover intention in Federal 0)

S/N	Item Description	Lik.	V. Lik.	Unlik.	V. Unlik.	SUM	Mean \bar{x}	sd	Remark
		1	2	3	4				
1.	How likely are you satisfied with the politics of your organization?	7	88	11	114	672	3.055	0.555	Unlikely
2.	How likely do you hope to leave your organization due to negative parties being played?	41	33	20	126	671	3.050	0.550	Unlikely
3.	How likely do you hope that the politics of your organization will improve soon?	1	21	83	115	752	3.418	0.918	Unlikely
4.	How likely do you hope of getting another job should it be offered to you?	7	88	5	120	678	3.082	0.582	Unlikely
5.	How likely can you contribute to the success of your organizational positive goals, should this opportunity be given to you?	188	16	15	1	269	1.220	-1.277	Likely

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2024)

Table 1 shows how likely organizational politics affects employee turnover intention in Federal University Dutsinma. The result shows that respondents were unlikely satisfied with the politics of their organization with the mean $\bar{x} = 3.055$ and the standard deviation $sd = 0.555$. Similarly they were not likely hoping to leave their organization due to negative parties being played with the mean $\bar{x} = 3.050$ and the standard deviation $sd = 0.550$.

However, respondents were unlikely hoping that the politics of their organization will improve soon with the mean $\bar{x} = 3.418$ and the standard deviation $sd = 0.918$. They were likely hoping of getting another job should it be offered to them with the mean $\bar{x} = 2.082$ and the standard deviation $sd = 0.418$. They were likely to contribute to the success of their organizational positive goals, should this opportunity be given to them with the mean $\bar{x} = 1.220$ and the standard deviation $sd = 1.277$.

5.1 Test of hypothesis.

(H_0^1) There is no relationship between organizational politics and employee turnover intention in Federal University Dutsinma.

Table 2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.942 ^a	.887	.886	.413	.887	1209.595	4	215	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), ORG_SUCCESS, ORG_REJECT_ANOTHER_JOB, ORG_IMPROVE, ORG_SATIS

Table 2 was the model summary for hypothesis one. The value of the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.887$ shows that there is strong positive relationship between organizational politics and employee turnover intention. The p-value = 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) shows that the result was significant which resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis. That is there is significant relationship between organizational politics and employee turnover intention.

Table 3 Linear regression coefficients for hypothesis.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.299	.167		7.756	.000
ORG_SATIS	.351	.112	.290	3.142	.002
1 ORG_IMPROVE	.451	.052	.252	8.628	.000
ORG_REJECT_ANOTHER_JOB	.515	.101	.430	5.120	.000
ORG_SUCCESS	.014	.030	.007	.464	.643

a. Dependent Variable: ORG_STAY_WITH

$$Y = 1.299 + 0.351x_1 + 0.451x_2 + 0.515x_3 + 0.014x_4$$

The regression equation above can be used to estimate or predict organizational politics on hoping to stay (y) based on how likely they are satisfied with the politics of their organization (x_1), how likely they hope that the politics of their organization will improve soon (x_2), how likely do you hope of rejecting another job should it be offered to them (x_3) and how likely can they contribute to the success of their organizational positive goals, should this opportunity be given to them (x_4). Any increase on how likely they are satisfied with the politics of their organization on hoping to stay will increase by 0.351 while other variable remained constant. Any increase on how likely they hope that the politics of their organization will improve soon, organizational politics on hoping to stay will decrease by 0.451 while other variable remained constant. Any increase on how likely they hope of rejecting another job should it be offered to them will increase by 0.515 while other variable remained constant. Any increase on how likely they can contribute to the success of their organizational positive goals, should this opportunity be given will increase by 0.014

In determining whether the model can be simplified, notice that P-values for the estimated coefficients of how likely they are satisfied with the politics of their organization is 0.002 which is less than the significance value (p-value < 0.05) indicating that they are significantly associated with turnover intention. Similarly, on how likely they hope that the politics of their organization will improve soon and how likely do they hope of rejecting another job should it be offered to them are both 0.000 which is less than the significant value (p-value < 0.05) indicating that they are significantly associated with employee turnover intention. While how likely can they contribute to the success of their organizational positive goals, should this opportunity be given to them is 0.643 which is greater than the significance value (p-value > 0.05) indicating that it is not significantly associated with organizational politics on hoping to stay.

Research Findings

Table 2 was the model summary for hypothesis one. The value of the coefficient of determination $R^2=0.887$ shows that there is strong positive relationship between organizational politics and employee turnover intention. The p-value = 0.000(p<0.05) shows that the result was very significant, which resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicated a significant relationship between organizational politic in relation to employee turnover intention in federal university Dutsinma.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The research recommended the followings

1. That organizational politics must be checked by creating proper control mechanisms by the National Universities Commission must be established by making sure that proper checking mechanisms are established in all federal universities to check the activities of organizational politics.
2. Players of organizational politic should be properly prosecuted to serve as a deterrent to those that want to follow suit

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